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ACHIEVEMENTS AND CHANGES IN THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY AS A RESULT OF CHINA'S FOREIGN TRADE POLICY

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Abstract: The scientific article analyzes the changes in the economy of China as a result of reforms in China's foreign trade policy since the late twentieth century, and the reasons for the dynamics of foreign trade turnover. At the same time, China's share of world exports for almost 30 years has been studied, as well as the factors that led to a sharp decline in GDP during the 2008 global financial crisis as a result of liberalization of foreign trade policy. This article is intended for economists, associate professors, professors, teachers, students majoring in economics, and those interested in economics.

Keywords: Liberalization, foreign trade, export, import, gross domestic product, China

Since China began its transition reform in 1978, a number of studies have been conducted in China to study the relationship between trade liberalization and the economy. There is a clear positive link between trade openness and economic growth. First, much of trade in China has decentralized and has become increasingly market-oriented. In addition, since China joined the World Trade Organization in 2001, most of the tariffs imposed by law have been sharply removed or reduced, and indirect taxes on exports have been abolished, which has increased imports and exports in China. Second, the growing competition entering China's domestic market has led to its economic growth. Trade liberalization has increased the flow of foreign direct investment into China, bringing new technologies and processes and increasing efficiency. Thanks to trade and investment reforms, foreign investment has become the most important source of economic growth and productivity in China. In 2007, there were 286,200 approved foreign investment companies in China, which employed about 42 million people and accounted for 31.5 percent of the value of gross industrial output. At the end of 2008, China became one of the world's largest destinations for attracting foreign investment. Third, after trade liberalization, China has become the world's largest trading power. According to World Trade Organization statistics, in 2006, total trade in goods accounted for

65 percent of China's GDP. Economic reforms and liberalization of trade and investment have helped make China a major trading power. The country's foreign trade turnover increased 198.8 times during the period - from \$ 20.64 billion in 1978 to \$ 4104.5 billion in 2017, including Chinese exports. 232 times, from \$ 9.75 to \$ 2,263.52 billion (Figure 1). China's yuan's foreign trade volume, trade, exports and imports will grow significantly. From 1979 to 2017, the country's average annual GDP growth was 9.5%.

Figure 1. China's foreign trade turnover (billion US dollars)¹

In the post-liberalization period, China has consistently risen to the top of world trade. In 1978, it ranked 29th in the world in terms of foreign trade turnover, in 1990 it rose to 16th, in 2000 to 8th, in 2010 to 2nd, and in 2013 has been ranked No. 1 (excluding 2016) since the United States in this regard. At the same time, in 2009, China overtook Germany to become the world leader in exports and the second largest importer after the United States. China's share of world exports increased from 2.0% in 1990 to 3.1% in 1995, 4.0% in 2000, 10.7% in 2010 and 13.2% in 2017. (Figure 1)

Figure 2. China's share in world commodity exports: 1990-2017²

¹ Zhongguo tujingsi zhayao 2017 [Xitoyning qisqacha statistikasi 2017]. Pekin, 2017. 94-bet (xitoy tilida).

² Manba: Economist Intelligence Unit.

Liberalization of foreign trade policy during an economic crisis can hurt the state. As a clear example of this, we can see the Chinese economy in the 2008 crisis.

Figure 3. China's GDP growth rate for 2006-2010³

After the global financial crisis, China's gross domestic product fell to 9.65% in 2008 and 9.4% in 2009, compared with a 13% positive increase in 2007. On the trade side, trade figures fell sharply due to the crisis. During the first ten months of 2008, the growth rates of exports and imports were 21.9%

³ China GDP Growth Rate 1961-2019. (2019). Macrotrends.net. Available from <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/CHN/china/gdp-growth-rate>.

and 27.6%, respectively. But in November, they fell by 2.2 percent and 17.9 percent, respectively. In the first half of 2009, Chinese exports fell by 21.8 percent and imports by 25.4 percent. The inflow of foreign investment also decreased by 12.6% in January-October 2009.

There are some reasons why globalization and liberalization have led to a sharp decline in trade during the financial crisis. First, the financial crisis in America has reduced demand for products exported from China. The World Bank said a 1 percent drop in U.S. GDP growth led to a 4.75 percent decline in China's export growth. Thus, the economic crisis has led to the bankruptcy of many export-oriented companies. The most important and worrying reason was trade protectionism by some countries, which affected the Chinese economy and led to the deterioration of the world trade environment. The opposite of trade liberalization is trade protection, which is the introduction of import duties or quotas to protect domestic industry from foreign competition. For example, in September 2009, the United States imposed a 35 percent tariff on \$ 1.8 billion worth of tire imports from China. . In addition, on February 5, 2010, the U.S. received antidumping duties of up to 231.4 percent for gift boxes and other types of ribbons. All of these safeguards have had a serious impact on China's growth and have had a negative impact on China's economic recovery. On the one hand, this has drastically reduced China's exports. On the other hand, trade restrictions also have a negative impact on imports. More than 30% of Chinese imports are spent on the production of export products, so when exports decrease due to trade protectionism, imports from other countries also decrease accordingly. In addition, trade protectionism has increased unemployment in China. For these reasons, we can see that trade liberalization is an important issue for the recovery of the global economy.

In general, trade liberalization has benefited the Chinese economy. It opened China's door to the world, brought competition and technology to China, and made China a major trading country. Low-cost labor and a fixed exchange rate have attracted foreign investors and dramatically boosted China's gross domestic product.

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